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**Team-Building Skills, Emotional Intelligence, and Decision-Making Skills
of Elected Barangay Officials**

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the levels of team-building skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making skills of Elected Barangay Officials in one of the cities in Negros Oriental for the Calendar Year 2022. This study used the descriptive research design to determine the levels of team-building skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making skills of Barangay Officials in one of the cities in Negros Oriental for the Calendar Year 2022, where 108 barangay officials will answer a self-made questionnaire which is validated and tested for reliability. Descriptive, comparative, and relational analytical are the analytical schemes and frequency and percentage, Mean, Mann-Whitney U Test, Spearman Rank-Order coefficient of Correlation, or Spearman rho as the Statistical tools. The results showed that younger and more senior respondents were evenly matched in number, with more respondents having served six years or more, and most were college graduates. The level of team-building skills of the elected barangay officials in all areas was "high." The level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials in all areas was likewise "high." Meantime, the level of decision-making skills of the same officials was likewise "high." When the respondents were grouped according to age, length of service, and highest educational attainment, the level of team-building skills of the elected barangay officials in communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving were also "high." Likewise, when the respondents were grouped according to age, length of service, and highest educational attainment, the level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials in the areas of self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and empathy was "high level." When the respondents were grouped according to age, length of service, and highest educational attainment, the level of decision-making skills of the elected barangay officials in the areas of interpersonal skills, collaboration skills, critical thinking skills, and active listening skills was "high level." No significant difference existed in the level of team-building skills of the elected barangay officials in the areas of communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving when grouped and compared according to age and length of service. While a significant difference existed in the level of team-building skills of the elected barangay officials in the area of teamwork when grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment. No significant difference existed in the level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials in the areas of self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and empathy when grouped and compared according to age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Moreover, no significant difference existed in the level of decision-making skills of the elected barangay officials in the areas of interpersonal skills, collaboration skills, critical thinking skills, and active listening skills when grouped and compared according to age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Further, a significant relationship exists between the level of team-building skills and the level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials. A significant relationship existed between the level of emotional intelligence and the level of decision making skills of the elected barangay officials. And a significant relationship existed between the level of team-building and the level of decision making skills of the elected barangay officials.

Keywords: Barangay Officials, Decision making, Emotional intelligence

Introduction:

The Local Government Code of the Philippines mandates elected Barangay Officials to enact local ordinances and work for the general welfare of their constituents. This is in addition to their other duties like legislating on tax and revenue, budget, infrastructures, etc., stipulated in Article 4, Section 392 of the Local Government Code (LGC). Side by side with their elected village chief (aka Punong Barangay), these Barangay Officials face the seemingly endless challenge of summoning their leadership and management skills in the exercises of their prime duties as servants of their people, day in and day out. One requisite of a public servant is team-building skills, which they need to apply not only with their constituents but also with their peers and other stakeholders. This kind of skill requires Barangay Officials to communicate their plans, build partnerships, and build an effective feedback mechanism with their target stakeholders. Building a cohesive team involves negotiating plans and intentions with the rest of the members of a team. Yet another requisite of a successful Barangay Official is emotional intelligence. They need the highest possible emotional intelligence as they deal with the diverse concerns of their constituencies and, at times, the political platforms of the parties they are affiliated with. By this, we mean the need to deal with themselves and others. Dealing with their very own selves and dealing with others can be one of the most challenging tasks an elected Barangay Official has to deal

with. But they are a fundamental requirement for a successful political career or commitment. Not only that. They also need to do self-management and relationship management if they are to establish their niche in their respective political turfs.

Elected barangay officials are leaders in themselves- nothing more, nothing less. They are constantly challenged to influence people- constituents, peers, other officials in the higher echelons of the government, civic leaders, or any other officials concerned with people's welfare. After all, leadership, in the words of John Todorovic (2016), is all about influencing others. In the words of Katz (p. 182), achieving this aim requires technical skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills. In light of the above discussion, the researcher sees the team-building skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making skills of elected Barangay Officials in Canlaon City, Negros Oriental, for the calendar year 2022. Findings that may be gathered from the study will serve as a substantial reference to a better understanding of the elected officials and can be replicated for the other elected officials in our country.

Objectives of the Study:

This study aimed to determine the levels of team-building skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making skills of Elected Barangay Officials in one of the cities in Negros Oriental for the Calendar Year 2022.

Literature Review:

Team-building Skills. Teams of people working together for a common purpose have been a centerpiece of the human social organization ever since our ancient ancestors first banded together to hunt game, raise families, and defend their communities, according to Kozlowski and Ilgen (2017) in an article published that same year. People working together in groups to explore, achieve, and conquer is a major part of human history. Although work as a collection of different jobs is primarily a tale of work in massive organizations that evolved in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. However, various global pressures have driven organizations worldwide to restructure work around teams to enable more quick, flexible and adaptive solutions to challenges over the last two decades. According to Naumovski et al. (2016), interpersonal communication is becoming one of the most critical factors for the development and establishment of public sector institutions and the development of society in all of its segments. It is a universally recognized value that works and can be used as an indicator for measuring the success and quality of public services through their users' lenses and eyes. Teams impact our lives daily, and their effectiveness is critical to our well-being in various societal activities. The processes that underpin team effectiveness have been studied for over 50 years—literally thousands of studies—and have been influenced. To increase the efficacy of work groups and teams, we intend to sift through this enormous literature to determine what we know, think we know, and need to know in this book. That motivation has the potential to make a difference regarding outcomes both on the individual and on the organizational level. The research subject is team building (team building) as an effective tool for forming a professional team Alla Zlenko & Elena Isaikina (2020).

Emotional Intelligence. Research on emotional intelligence (EI) suggests that it is associated with more pro-social behavior, better academic performance, and improved empathy toward patients. In medical education and clinical practice, EI has been related to higher academic achievement and improved doctor-patient relationships. What famous research has been done in the field of emotional intelligence?

Daniel Goleman's work has introduced millions of people to the idea and concept of emotional intelligence. While Salovey and Mayer may have coined the term EI, Goleman popularized it through his work and books. Self-awareness is a way of thinking of a person about himself, his authority, responsibility, and targets in facing and resolving a problem so that the tasks and problems they carry can be resolved. That is why a person's awareness will significantly affect their organizational performance. When an individual has good Self Awareness, the individual can control himself by reading social situations to understand others and understanding others about him (Putri, Tazkiyah & Amelia, 2019).

Salovey and Grewal (2015) wrote an article entitled the science of emotional intelligence that got published in the *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 14(6), 281–285. This article gives a summary of current emotional intelligence research. Although emotional intelligence has been described in various ways, we focus on Mayer and Salovey's (2018) four-branch model, which defines it as a set of four connected abilities: sensing, using, understanding, and managing emotions. Individual differences in capacities connected to processing emotional information can be studied using this notion as a framework. Enough evidence for emotional intelligence has been accumulated, despite measurement challenges. Emotional intelligence predicts success in various areas, including personal and professional relationships. EI emerged as a major psychological construct in the early 1990s, where it was conceptualized as a set of abilities largely analogous to general intelligence. Early influential work on EI was conducted by Salovey and Mayer (1990), who defined EI as "the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions" (p. 189). They argued that individuals high in EI had certain emotional abilities and skills related to appraising and regulating emotions in the self and others. Accordingly, it was argued that individuals high in EI could accurately perceive certain emotions in themselves and others (e.g., anger, sadness) and also regulate emotions in themselves and others in order to achieve a range of adaptive outcomes or emotional states (e.g., motivation, creative thinking).

Research Method:**Research Design**

This study uses the descriptive research design to determine the level of team-building skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making skills of elected Barangay Officials in one of the cities in Negros Oriental for the Calendar Year 2022. Bueno (2016) claimed that the descriptive research design is appropriate for studies that aim to discover what prevails in the present conditions or relationships, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. It also seeks to determine relationships between or among study variables, explores causes of phenomena, tests hypotheses, and develops generalizations, principles, or theories based on findings. While the conditions and things during the study are its primary concern, it also considers prior events and influences deemed relevant to what is being examined.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are 108 elected Barangay Officials from the 12 Barangays. Since the total number of respondents is manageable, the researcher utilizes purposive sampling. The table below shows the distribution of respondents per Barangay.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Barangays	Population (N)	Percentage (%)
A	9	8.333
B	9	8.333
C	9	8.333
D	9	8.333
E	9	8.333
F	9	8.333
G	9	8.333
H	9	8.333
I	9	8.333
J	9	8.333
K	9	8.333
L	9	8.333
Total	108	100%

Data Gathering Instrument

This study uses a self-made questionnaire to gather the data from subject-respondents. The questionnaire consists of two parts.

Part 1 contains respondents' demographic profiles such as age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Part II is the questionnaire proper, which consists of levels of team-building skills analyzed in terms of communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving; emotional intelligence analyzed in terms of self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and empathy; and decision-making skills analyzed in terms of interpersonal skills, collaboration skills, critical thinking skills, and active listening skills. There were five (5) questions in each area under team-building skills, emotional intelligence, and decision-making skills for 60 items in a survey questionnaire. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, using a 5-point Likert scale with 5 as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely, and 1 as almost never.

Validity

Facundo et al. (2020) define validity as the extent to which the interpretations of the results of a test are warranted, which depends on the particular use of the test intended to serve. Thus, the research instrument will be subjected to face validation from experts in the field of research. Chosen five (5) experts in research and public administration will validate the instrument using the criteria set by Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates. The interpretation is as follows: Excellent (4.21 - 5.00); Very Good (3.41 - 4.20); Good (2.61-3.40); Fair (1.81 - 2.60); Poor (1.00-1.80). The first validator is a retired LGU administrator, Canlaon City, a graduate of Doctor of Public Administration major in Administration and Supervision. The second validator is the LGU Administrator of Canlaon City and a graduate of Doctor of Medicine. The third validator is a former City Councilor, a graduate of Master of Public Administration. The

fourth validator is an expert Division Supervisor of Bacolod City, a graduate of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management. The Final Validator is a graduate of the Doctor of Education, the Dean of the College of Education in one of the Colleges in Silay City, and an Expert in Public Administration. For this study, the Validity score is 4.77, interpreted as Excellent.

Reliability

In the words of Ghazali (2016), reliability is the degree to which an assessment tool produces stable and consistent results. It is the degree of consistency or stability of research to produce or yield the same results. Cronbach's alpha measures the internal consistency or reliability between several items, measurements, or ratings. In other words, it estimates how reliable the responses of a questionnaire (or domain of a questionnaire), instrumentation, or rating are evaluated by subjects, indicating the stability of the tools. Alpha was developed by Cronbach (1) and was initially used to measure the reliability of a psychometric instrument. The value of Cronbach's alpha ranges from zero (0) to one (1), with the higher values implying that the items measure the same dimension. In contrast, if Cronbach's alpha value is low (near 0), some or all the things are not measuring the same dimension (Bujang et al., 2018). Once Cronbach's alpha value reaches 0.70 to 1.00, the research instrument is considered reliable. To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher used Cronbach's Alpha after administering the survey questionnaire to 30 elected Barangay Officials among six randomly selected Barangays in Bacolod City. For this study, the team-building skills reliability index is 0.941, interpreted as "Excellent," the emotional intelligence reliability index is 0.876, interpreted as "Good," and the decision-making skills reliability index is 0.880, interpreted as "Good," meaning the questionnaire is highly reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

At the onset, the researcher requests permission through written communication from the City Mayor through channels of Canlaon City, Negros Oriental. Once granted, the researcher distributes the research instruments to each respondent. After retrieving the filled survey questionnaires, the responses will be encoded and subjected to data analysis. Computations will then be done with Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed as per consideration of the objectives that are stated in this study. Analytical Schemes This study employs three analytical schemes based on the research objectives- descriptive, comparative, and relational.

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service.

Objective No. 2 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of team-building skills of the Elected Barangay Officials according to communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving.

Objective No. 3 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials according to self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and empathy.

Objective No. 4 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of decision-making skills of the Elected Barangay Officials according to interpersonal, collaboration, critical thinking, and active listening skills.

Objective No. 5 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of team-building skills of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 7 likewise used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of decision-making skills of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 8 used the comparative analytical scheme to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of team-building skills of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 9 likewise used the comparative analytical scheme to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the Elected Barangay Officials' emotional intelligence level when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 10 also used the comparative analytical scheme to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of decision-making skills of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 11 used the relational analytical scheme to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of team-building skills and the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials.

Objective No. 12 also used the relational analytical scheme to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of emotional intelligence and decision-making skills of Elected Barangay Officials.

Objective No. 13 likewise used the relational analytical scheme to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of decision-making skills and team-building skills of Elected Barangay Officials.

Statistical Tools

Objective No. 1 used the frequency count and percentage scoring to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and length of service. A frequency count determines how many people fall into a certain group or how frequently a particular trait occurs. Both the absolute (actual number) and relative (%) totals are used to represent this calculation (Davis, 2021). While Percentage is calculated by dividing the frequency in the category by the total number of participants and multiplying by 100%.

Objective No. 2 used the mean to determine the level of team-building skills of the Elected Barangay Officials according to communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving. The mean is the most used measure of central Tendency. The mean is computed by adding scores and dividing the sum by the number of individuals. According to Glass and Hopkins (2015), the mean is considered the most accurate of the measures of central tendency. To measure the level of team-building skills of elected Barangay Officials, the following mean scoring and verbal interpretation were used:

Mean scoring	Verbal Interpretation
4.50 - 5.00	Very High Level
3.50 - 4.49	High Level
2.50 - 3.49	Moderate Level
1.50 - 2.49	Low Level
1.00 - 1.49	Very Low Level

Objective No. 3 also used the mean to determine the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials according to self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and self-management, empathy.

Objective No. 4 also used the mean to determine the level of decision-making skills of the Elected Barangay Officials according to interpersonal, collaboration, critical thinking, and active listening skills.

Objective No. 5 likewise used the mean to determine the level of team-building skills of the Barangay Officials when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 also used the mean to determine the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 7 likewise used the mean to determine the level of decision-making skills of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 8 used the Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of team-building skills of the Barangay Officials when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. The non-parametric alternative test to the independent sample t-test is the Mann-Whitney U Test. It is a non-parametric test used to assess whether two sample means are equal or not when comparing two sample means drawn from the same population. The Mann-Whitney U test is typically employed when the data is ordinal or when the t-test's assumptions are broken. The data do not provide any justification for rejecting the null hypothesis if the p-value is high (Sander, 2016).

Objective No. 9 also used the Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 10 likewise used the Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether or not a significant difference exists in the level of decision-making skills of the Elected Barangay Officials when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 11 used the Spearman Rho to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of team-building skills and the level of emotional intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials.

Spearman Rho (ρ), also called Spearman rank order correlation coefficient, is a non-parametric measure of the strength of association that exists between two variables measured on an ordinal scale and is used to test the association between two ranked variables, or one ranked variable and one measurement variable (Frey, 2018). According to Johnson and Kuby (2015), if the p-value is greater than the level of significance, then the decision must be to fail to reject the null hypothesis. If the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance, then the decision must be to reject the null hypothesis.

Objective No. 12 likewise made use of the Spearman Rho to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of emotional intelligence and decision-making skills of Elected Barangay Officials. Finally, Objective No. 13 also used the Spearman Rho to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of decision-making and team-building skills of Elected Barangay Officials.

Ethical Considerations

All research studies must consider the protection of human subjects by implementing the proper ethical standards. Due to the extensive nature of the study process in a qualitative study, ethical questions have a special resonance (Arifin, 2018).

Findings and Discussion:

Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

The study's first objective aimed to determine the profile of the respondents according to age, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Table 2 presents the results.

Table 2

Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 49 years old)	54	50.00
	Older (49 years old and above)	54	50.00
	Total	108	100
Length of Service	Shorter (less than six years)	36	33.30
	Longer (6 years and more)	72	66.70
	Total	108	100
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower (Elementary and High School)	44	40.70
	Higher (College)	64	59.30
	Total	108	100

As presented in Table 2, 54 or 50.0% are younger respondents (below 49 years old), while older respondents (49 years old and above) contributed to half of the population. Regarding the length of service, 72, or 66.7% of the respondents, had served for more than six years, while 36, or 33.3%, had served for less than six years. Further, for the highest educational attainment, 44 or 40.7% are elementary and high school graduates, while 64 or 59.3% are college graduates. It implies that both younger and older respondents contributed to half of the study's participants; many respondents had served for more than six years, and many of them were college graduates.

Level of Team-building Skills of Elected Barangay Officials according to Communication, Teamwork, Motivation, and Problem-Solving

The study's second objective aimed to determine the level of team-building skills of the elected barangay officials according to the following areas: communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving. Tables 3-6 show that data.

Table 3

Level of Team-building Skills of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Communication

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. see to it that I communicate all the activities in the barangay.	4.49	Very High Level
2. confer with my constituents' areas that needed outright attention.	4.46	High Level
3. clarify gray areas that must be addressed.	4.49	Very High Level
4. Listen to all sides to be fair to everyone.	4.47	High Level

5. motivate them to be more participative and involved in all activities	4.48	High Level
Overall Mean	4.48	High Level

As presented in Table 3, the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 4.48, interpreted as "high level." It only shows that most of the elected barangay officials have excellent team-building skills in terms of communication. However, if we go deeper into the analysis, respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.49 on items No. 1 and 3 which states, "see to it that I communicate all the activities in the barangay" and "clarify gray areas that must be addressed upon" interpreted as "very high level." On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.46 was on item No. 2, which states, "confer with my constituents' areas which needed outright attention" and is interpreted as "high level." This implies that some elected barangay officials are less active in conferring with their constituents about areas that need outright attention. This is because some areas/purok/sites need ample time to travel, especially in highland areas, which caused the delay in providing the constituents' needs. However, the elected barangay officials tried to respond immediately to the constituents' concerns. This result was supported by Naumovski et al. (2016), which state that interpersonal communication is becoming one of the most critical factors for the development and establishment of public sector institutions and the development of society in all of its segments. It is a universally recognized value that works and can be used as an indicator for measuring the success and quality of public services through their users' lens and eyes.

Table 4*Level of Team-building Skills of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Teamwork*

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. initiate planning sessions.	4.33	High Level
2. lead in the execution of planned activities.	4.38	High Level
3. motivate them to be actively involved in all activities.	4.36	High Level
4. Consult my constituents on how to execute team-building activities.	4.37	High Level
5. see to it that everybody is working together with the planned activities	4.32	High Level
Overall Mean	4.35	High Level

The results in Table 4 disclosed wherein the respondents assessed an overall mean score was 4.35 and interpreted it as "high level." This shows that most of the elected barangay officials have very good team-building skills in terms of teamwork development. If we investigate the results further, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.38 on item No. 2, which states, "lead in the execution of planned activities" and interpreted as "high level." In contrast, the lowest mean of 4.32 was item No. 5, which states, "see to it that everybody is working together with the planned activities" and interpreted as "high level." The results imply that some elected barangay officials were less active in planning barangay activities. As an elected official, you must show enthusiasm and passion to work. You must act to help the team to attain the objectives through the maximum application of its capabilities. The elected barangay officials must place themselves before the team as they facilitate progress and inspire the team to accomplish the goals and objectives of the barangay. Teamwork strengthens relationships. Each member relies on the other and builds trust. Hence, trust encourages them to work together again despite minor disagreements and solve problems. Tripathy (2018) strongly agrees when he says that a strong bond is shared, which overcomes even minor conflicts. Trust among team members provides a feeling of security and creates cohesion. Each member recognizes the distinct abilities each of them possesses, and this helps them to move ahead with their relationships.

Table 5*Level of Team-building Skills of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Motivation*

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. recognize each barangay official.	4.30	High Level
2. encourage them to use their potential.	4.33	High Level
3. involved them in initiating activities.	4.32	High Level
4. provide good feedback for their accomplishments.	4.28	High Level
5. conduct Focus Group Discussion about their shared ideas.	4.29	High Level
Overall Mean	4.30	High Level

Table 5 revealed the results wherein the level of team-building skills of the elected barangay officials in motivation was high. This is supported by the respondents' responses with an overall mean score of 4.30 which is interpreted as "high level." However, if we examine further the items in Table 5, respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.33 on item No. 2, which states "encourage them to use their potentials," interpreted as "high level." The lowest mean of 4.28 was on item No. 4, which says, "conduct Focus Group Discussion about their shared ideas," interpreted as "high level." Based on the results, it implies that not all elected barangay officials provide good feedback on the accomplishments of their co-officials. This is because there are barangays which has political rivals among barangay officials. Hence, good feedback on the accomplishments and achievements coming from other barangay officials was less. The result is supported by the claims of Ritz et al. (2016). According to them, motivation in public

service is the desire to behave according to motives grounded in the public interest to serve society. The idea is that public officials should be concerned with the public interest, leaving aside individual interests.

Table 6*Level of Team-building Skills of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Problem-Solving*

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. conduct sessions on problem-solving strategies.	4.23	High Level
2. listen intently to their ideas.	4.23	High Level
3. lead them in their ability to create choices.	4.20	High Level
4. mentor them in different problem-solving sessions.	4.17	High Level
5. collaborate with their presented ideas.	4.19	High Level
Overall Mean	4.20	High Level

As divulged in Table 6, the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 4.20, interpreted as "high level." It is presumed that most of the elected barangay officials had good problem-solving skills in dealing with concerns and issues in the barangay. As shown in Table 6, the respondents gave the highest mean score of 4.23 on items No. 1 and 2, which states, "conduct sessions on problem-solving strategies" and "listen intently to their ideas," interpreted as "high level." On the other hand, the lowest mean of 4.17 was on item 4, which states, "mentor them on different problem-solving sessions" and is interpreted as "high level." This implies that some elected barangay officials no longer mentor their colleagues in different problem-solving sessions. However, they listen to the ideas of their colleagues and choose the best strategies to solve the problems of the barangay. Kapur (2022) positively pointed out and supported the findings of this study that the problems need to be solved and prevented from assuming a major form. Hence, all the members of the organization need to emphasize honing problem-solving skills. The issues can be solved on one's own or through obtaining support from their colleagues. The members need to communicate effectively and form cordial and amiable terms and relationships with others. The individuals need to make provision of factual information. Therefore, implementing effective communication processes are an indispensable method of honing problem-solving skills.

Level of Emotional Intelligence of the Elected Barangay Officials according to the areas of Self-awareness, Self-regulation, Self-management, and Empathy

The third objective of the study aimed to determine the level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials according to the following areas of self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and empathy. Tables 7 – 10 show that data.

Table 7*Level of Emotional Intelligence of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Self-awareness*

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. introduce them to different strategies.	4.28	High Level
2. make sure that each official exercises calmness and sobriety.	4.25	High Level
3. introduce self-based analysis on how to be calm and composed.	4.23	High Level
4. Lead in some mock sessions that test calmness.	4.19	High Level
5. allow them to be exposed to choices to determine their self-worth.	4.16	High Level
Overall Mean	4.22	High Level

In the area of self-awareness, Table 7 shows that the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 4.22 and interpreted it as a "high level." In these results, we could say that the majority of the elected barangay officials displayed a high level of emotional intelligence in terms of self-awareness. However, if we inspect Table 7 further, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.28 on item No. 1 which states "introduce them to different strategies" and interpreted as "high level," while the lowest mean of 4.16 was on item No. 5 which states "allow them to be exposed to choices to determine their self-worth" and interpreted as "high level." This implies that there are some elected barangay officials are hesitant to expose their choice of strategies with the barangay affairs in order to avoid misunderstanding with other officials, especially the one handling the chairmanship in a certain committee. However, they make sure that each official exercises calmness and sobriety during barangay sessions. Being aware of how we can appear to others, we are more likely to adhere to social norms and behave in ways that are socially acceptable. Self-awareness is a way of thinking of a person about himself, his authority, responsibility, and targets in facing and resolving a problem so that the tasks and problems they carry can be resolved. The results of this study were supported by (Putri, Tazkiyah, and Amelia, 2019). When he said that a person's awareness will greatly affect their performance in the organization.

Table 8

Level of Emotional Intelligence of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Self-regulation

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. see to it that I become a role model.	4.16	High Level
2. control my temper on conflicting issues.	4.18	High Level
3. actively process the suggestions of others.	4.18	High Level
4. manifest self-control even on opposing issues.	4.15	High Level
5. show respect for varied opinions.	4.16	High Level
Overall Mean	4.16	High Level

Table 8 exposes the result wherein the level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials in the area of self-regulation was high. This finding is supported by the responses of the participants with an overall mean score of 4.16 which is interpreted as "high level." However, if we go deeper in the analysis, respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.18 on items No. 2 and 3 which states "control my temper on conflicting issues" and actively process suggestion of others" interpreted as "high level." Whereas the lowest mean of 4.15 was on item No. 4 which states "manifest self-control even on opposing issues" interpreted as "high level." Based on the results, it implies that some elected barangay officials sometimes could not control their emotions when opposing certain issues related to barangay affairs during sessions and meetings. However, they acknowledged both parties' suggestions to avoid conflict and resolve the problem with a win-win solution. Papenfub and Schmidt (2020) support this result when they say that self-regulation is a valuable governance mechanism with special advantages in terms of flexibility to address severe governance challenges such as insufficient political control, lack of accountability, and unclear areas of responsibility.

Table 9*Level of Emotional Intelligence of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Self-management*

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. I am always calm and impartial in my dealings.	4.19	High Level
2. I am always punctual in all meetings/sessions.	4.25	High Level
3. present ideas based on their suggestions.	4.18	High Level
4. conduct myself to be an official of character.	4.17	High Level
5. make an analysis of their actions.	4.19	High Level
Overall Mean	4.19	High Level

As depicted in Table 9, the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 4.19, interpreted as "high level." However, if we examine further the items in Table 9, the respondents assessed the highest mean of 4.25 on item No. 2, which states, "am always punctual in all meetings/sessions" and interpreted as "high level." On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 4.17 was item No. 4, which states, "conduct me to be an official of character," interpreted as "high level." This implies that some elected barangay officials are less obedient in the conduct of becoming an official of character. This is because some elected barangay officials have poor self-management skills. As an elected barangay official, he must discharge his duties with utmost responsibility, integrity, competence, and loyalty, act with patriotism and justice, lead modest lives, and uphold public interest over personal interest. Self-management skills are your ability to regulate and control your actions, feelings, and thoughts. With these skills, you can follow through on the work you're supposed to be doing. Likewise, being able to manage yourself can help you be more successful in your goal-setting efforts. David (2017) strongly affirmed the results that self-management is a key skill that will help individuals throughout their life. It involves setting goals and managing time. Developing motivation and concentration skills will help individuals to overcome the lure of procrastination. Effective self-management will help to avoid stress and provide more opportunities to get involved in the workplace activities.

Table 10*Level of Emotional Intelligence of Elected Barangay Officials in the area of Empathy*

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As an elected barangay official, I...		
1. support their actions.	4.24	High Level
2. extend assistance on whatever needs they have.	4.23	High Level
3. listen intently to their ideas.	4.24	High Level
4. activate their sense of belonging.	4.24	High Level
5. consider their feelings and respect them.	4.31	High Level
Overall Mean	4.25	High Level

Table 10 shows the results wherein the level of emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials in the area of empathy was high. These findings are supported by the responses of the respondents with an overall mean score of 4.25, which is interpreted as "high level." However, if we conduct more detailed results, respondents assessed the highest mean of 4.31 on item No. 5, which states, "consider their feelings and respect them" interpreted as "high level." The lowest mean score of 4.23 was on item No. 2, which states, "extend assistance on whatever needs they have," interpreted as "high level." This implies that some elected barangay officials were less capable of extending assistance to their colleagues and constituents that needed outright attention. This is because not all the time's elected

barangay officials can handle difficult situations. However, they show empathy by supporting colleagues' actions and ideas for the betterment of the barangay. According to Zangmo (2018), empathy is the ability to recognize, understand, and respond to the feelings of another, offers a way to improve these interactions and bring those more in line with expected public service values. He supports the results and says that empathetic behavior is widely regarded as important in achieving positive outcomes. Empathy has played an important role in better serving the citizens encouraging future learning, and developing social relationships. While the lack of empathy has also been related to the development of problem behaviors.

Conclusion:

On the bases of the foregoing findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions: Most of the elected barangay officials exhibited high team-building skills, especially in communication, teamwork, motivation, and problem-solving.

Most of the elected barangay officials possess a high level of emotional intelligence regarding self-awareness, self-regulation, self-management, and empathy.

Most elected barangay officials displayed a high level of decision-making skills concerning interpersonal, collaboration, critical thinking, and active listening skills.

The team-building skills of the elected barangay officials in performing their duties did not vary regardless of their age and length of service. The highest educational attainment can influence their team-building skills in teamwork.

The emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials did not differ regardless of their age, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

In addition, the decision-making skills of the elected barangay officials as not affected by their profile variables' age, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

Further, the emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials directly/indirectly contributes to good team-building skills. The emotional intelligence of the elected barangay officials may influence their decision-making. And the team-building skills of the elected barangay officials may affect their decision-making skills.

Limitations and Further Research:

It is highly recommended that barangay officials must gather their heads together to tackle issues that arise. They must out rightly address any issue concerning their barangays to effect speedy resolution of any problem and manifest to the people that they performed their avowed duties and responsibilities as stipulated in the local government code. In view of the findings in Table 4, "see to it that everybody is working together with planned activities."

It is strongly recommended that Barangay officials create teamwork where each idea becomes a trigger point of discussion in planning activities. Moreover, it is necessary for everyone to actively participate in the discussion to arrive at a common and acceptable decision. It is recommended that shared ideas, opinions, and observations of Barangay officials must be "laid down to a discussion table" so that decisions that may be arrived at will have the ownership of each participant. This is to avoid further discussion and confusion among officials. It is recommended that officials be mentored through consultancy sessions, group dynamics, and even small session forms to substantiate what they already know and maximize their potential to achieve quality decisions for their constituents. Officials must feel their significance and relevance in every work they do. This is one way to recognize their performance and contribution to the results of any endeavor. Self-worth is a great motivational factor for them to continue their eagerness and pride in their worth in any activity. Human beings are complex, so with each official, however, it is necessary that one must observe proper decorum in addressing issues of the barangay affairs. Self-control is an indication that a person has a sound mind, disposition, and with professionalism. Barangay officials must act as a professional they should not get into trouble that could demean or question their position. Hence, they should always observe value-laded character for everyone to emulate and follow. It is recommended that all officials be responsible for their constituents' needs regardless of who they voted for in the previous elections or what other affiliations they have. Be a true leader and become a model in words, tarpaulins, flyers, thoughts, and deeds. It is recommended that officials must be impartial in all their dealings so that biases can be avoided. Also, they should take time to listen very carefully so that they can weigh important issues that could empower everybody to become creative problem solvers and a solution rather than a problem in the organization. All officials must always see to it that issues and concerns result be known and dissociated to the barangay. This is necessary in order for everyone to be aware of the issue and become an agent of change. Awareness by everybody will result in more active participation in the community, which will be endowed with great success. It is recommended that officials shall undergo training on problem-solving skills. This training may be initiated by the LGU in the locality. A workshop session is also necessary in order for them to experience decision-making and to process the ways how to address those issues arising from the problems.

It is recommended that a workshop on solving issues through a qualitative "theme-building development" be conducted for all officials. Their qualitative approach way comes in the form of dyads or triads where situations are presented, decoded, and themed. This exercise may be helpful for officials to put together disagreements into one solid decision.

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